

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *A serious inflammatory disease of the mucous membranes of the nose is accompanied by disproportionate, acute rhinosinusitis, which often surprises women. The duration of the therapeutic period can be one month. As a result of inflammation of the mucous membrane, the mucus begins to thicken. In the cavity, a purulent exudate begins. As a result, acute rhinosinusitis occurs.*

Keywords: *allergic rhinosinusitis, atrophic rhinosinusitis, purulent rhinosinusitis, catarrhal form, diagnostics.*

The dominant factor in this condition is acute Adenovirus, the flu has not been treated to the end. As a result, the removal of mucus from the nose is blocked. Due to its stagnation, the reproduction of pathogenic microorganisms begins.

Provocative agents of purulent rhinosinusitis:

- Bacteria (the most common streptococci, blue pockets,);
- Gensular Candida representatives are like yeast.
- Aerobic mold fungi of the genus *Aspergillus*.

To elaborate on the details is to consider the reasons that lead to its development. There can be some particular causes that lead to and they are enlisted below:

- Mucous membrane - polyps, etc. Neoplasms;
- Bronchial asthma;
- Allergy;
- Decreased immunity;
- Damage to the nose or its congenital curvature;
- Falling of foreign objects into the nasal passage;
- Heredity;
- Consequences of drug therapy;

Depending on the effect of inflammation, the following types of rhinosinusitis are distinguished such as viral, bacterial, mushroom. In the most serious cases, a mixed type of disease can be diagnosed. According to the disease process, the following types can be considered such as sharp, repetitive, chronic rhinosinusitis.

The chronic form may not be until the end of the acute type of cystitis. The course of the disease is distinguished by smoking, alcohol consumption, pathologies of the oral cavity.

- a) According to the severity of the pathology, there some more types are enlisted with their peculiarities. There three forms are distinguished as follows:
- b) Easy, accompanied by a small temperature rise;
- c) Palpation of the nasal sinuses is characterized by the appearance of pain during palpation. The patient complains of headache;

The severe form is associated with severe pain, pus, and swelling of the nose. According to the place, On localization of the center of inflammation unilateral and bilateral rhinosinusitis are distinguished.

Characteristic symptoms

Regardless of the patient's age, the symptoms of acute rhinosinusitis are the same, which allows you to understand the severity of the disease and seek medical help in time:

The difference in symptoms can be explained by the zone of the lesion. For example, these zones are described as follows:

A painful syndrome directed to the forehead area testifies to a sharp face;

Severe pain with a pulling sensation in the nasal sinus section is a symptom of acute mademitis;

Painful headaches can be symptoms of senenidal development;

Solipose Rhinosinusitis

The development of soliposis rhinosinusitis is due to the weakening of immunity and immunoglobulin deficiency. As the disease develops against the background of the enemy, the epithelial tissue thickens with the gradual growth of polyps. It is impossible to treat such a pathology, so an operation is prescribed to restore nasal breathing.

Purulent rhinosinusitis

Acute pinosinusitis in adults and children is localized in the epithelium of the inner surfaces of the nose.

To treat the inflammatory focus, the severity of the purulent process, antibacterial therapy is required. Accurate diagnosis is based on the grid of accumulations in the corner of the nose and their planting. Reading analyzes allow you to determine the type of pathogen -, streptococci, etc., and prescribe the appropriate treatment.

A therapeutic complex with a purulent course of the disease includes depending on several types of drugs.

Complex immunomodulators (for example, immunity) with MultiVitamin preparations (reluctance, violence, increasingly, etc.). They promote the activation of the defense mechanism, strengthening the body.

Antihistamines to reduce swelling. At the same time, they reduce the amount of mucus that prevents free breathing. A good effect in treatment shows Tumeql, Claritin, Loratadine. Provide inflammation, moisten the mucous membranes of the nose to the nose - vibration, polydx. Galazolin, Deryvin, Naftizin have a crusty effect.

Nulcolians promoting the formation of a sticky secret. Mojdin, Flujex, flosHumucil are often prescribed.

Antibacterial agents designed to eliminate infection. At the first signs, Amoxicillin has a high anti-inflammatory effect. If the disease is diagnosed, acute treatment with purulent foci of inflammation requires the introduction of strong antibiotics of tetracycline varieties. Without proper treatment, the development of purulent rhinosinusitis can lead to dangerous conditions, in the form of meningitis and various severity of abscesses.

Catarrhal form

A sharp development in the background of breathing in the focus of inflammation in the mucous membranes of the turn (Row) and in the sinuses made (Row). When diagnosing an acute

catarrhal process, the therapeutic process passes quickly, but it can lead to consequences that have already begun.

In addition to general symptoms, catarrhal headaches are characterized by localization of headaches in the foreheads, characterized by headaches in the foreheads. Obviously, the double ralosine of suffering brings more. A complex course leads to the development of insomnia, the appearance of neurasthenia, memory loss.

Treated at the initial stage of "Cararhal" (Eferon, Anaafon, Amijon). They remove the first symptoms. They will not be useful in the later stages of the disease.

"Antihistamine" (Diazolin, Tuevel, Larataine) is used to fight catarrhal rhinosinusitis. Their task was that there were no drugs to reduce the swelling.

During the catarrhal form, mucus secretion is usually minimal. But if there are annoying moments, then the treatment of rhinosinusitis includes vasoconstrictive nasal drops. Vitamins and increased immunity require medication. Sometimes the chronic course of the disease leads to surgical intervention.

Under local anesthesia, it is ordered to clean the attachment cake with the help of lameness.

Vasomotor form

In the cold, vasomotor rhinosinusitis develops, can have bilateral and unilateral defeat. This disease is characterized by a violation of the tone of the vessels. It is about the swelling next to the lying mucous membrane. Its swelling causes nasal congestion.

The causes of the vasomotor inflammatory process are unfavorable external environment. In women, this condition may be due to hormonal changes. In delayed treatment, and in children and adults, rhinosinusitis is a complex and acute process that requires more time than in acute forms. Depending on the size, the doctor prescribes washing, antibiotics, etc.

Allergic rhinosinusitis

Allergic rhinosinusitis symptoms and treatment depend on the inflammation of the allergen, accompanied by itching with nasal passages, watery discharge, swelling.

Treatment of rhinosinusitis begins, the doctor prescribes a special test that detects allergens in samples. This allows you to continue special preventive measures to eliminate certain products or substances from the body.

Diagnostics

Before treating rhinosinusitis, the otorhinolaryngologist conducts a visual examination of the patient. Symptoms are identified during the interview. Palpation of the zones on the forehead and nose will reveal the painful parts.

Various surveys were conducted in Rinoinka:

- Rostoscopy - picking the nose with mirrors.
- Otoscopy - the use of a light source to obtain information about the condition of the mucous membranes;
- Pharzososcopy is an examination of the nasopharynx using mirrors;
- radiography;
- MRI;
- CT scan.

Accepts Christian content for laboratory research. After a comprehensive study during chronic or acute flow, an accurate diagnosis is made and a set of drugs is selected.

There are some features of treatment in children which will be discussed below. In the case of acute rhinosinusitis or in chronic form, children are prescribed only the prescribed dose of drugs and some things recommended for adults are excluded.

Treatment of complex rhinosinusitis requires complete and implementation according to all recommendations.

Physiotherapy

In addition to tablets, drops, rinses, physiotherapeutic procedures are included in the medical complex. They contribute to reducing the inflammatory process. With vasomotor rhinosinusitis, it helps to wash the nasal cavities with special solutions. If the catarrhal form is detected, such physiotherapeutic measures as UHF, electrophoresis, didinila currents are indicated. Finding the use of a laser to strengthen the nasal walls, improve the tone of blood vessels. Self-treatment for any form of rhinosinusitis is impossible, because this disease is complex and requires a competent approach to the appointment of therapeutic procedures.

REFERENCES

1. Абдурахмонов И. Р., Шамсиев Д. Ф. БОШ МИЯ ФАЛАЖИ ФОНИДАГИ ПАРАНАЗАЛ СИНУСИТЛАРНИ ДАВОЛАШДА ЎЗИГА ХОС ЁНДАШИШ //MedUnion. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 14-26.
2. Абдурахманов, И. Р., Х. Н. Тураев, and Д. Ф. Шамсиев. "Болаликдан бош мия фалажи фонида риносинусити бор беморларда бурун бўшлиғи мукоцилиар транспорти назорати тўғрисидаги замонавий қарашлар (адабиётлар шарҳи)." журнал «Биомедицины и практики 7.2 (2022): 259-267.
3. Абдурахманов, И., Шамсиев, Д., & Олимжонова, Ф. (2022). ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ МУКОРЕГУЛЯРНЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ОСТРОГО И ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ПАРАНАЗАЛЬНОГО СИНУСИТА ПРИ ДЕТСКОМ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНОМ ПАРАЛИЧЕ. Журнал стоматологии и краниофациальных исследований, 2(2), 18–21. <https://doi.org/10.26739.2181-0966-2021-2-3>
4. Абдурахмонов, Илхом Рустамович. "Тураев Хикматулло Негматович опыт применения синупрета с антибактериальными препаратами в комплексной терапии риносинуситов у больных детским церебральным параличом." Достижения науки и образования 2 (2022): 82.
5. Тураев Хикматилла Негматович, Абдурахмонов Илхом Рустамович ВЛИЯНИЕ БУДЕСОНИДА НА КАЧЕСТВО ЖИЗНИ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С БРОНХИАЛЬНЫМ ОБСТРУКТИВНЫМ СИНДРОМОМ // Вопросы науки и образования. 2021. №7 (132). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/vliyanie-budesonida-na-kachestvo-zhizni-patsientov-s-bronhialnym-obstruktivnym-sindromom> (дата обращения: 09.10.2023).
6. Абдурахманов И., Шамсиев Д., Олимжонова Ф.(2021) Болаликдан бош мия фалажи билан болалардаги ўткир ва сурункали параназал синуситларни даволашда мукорегуляр дори воситасини самарадорлигини ўрганиш // Журнал стоматологии и краниофациальных исследований, Том2, №2, стр. 18-21
7. Абдурахмонов И. Р., Шамсиев Д. Ф. БОШ МИЯ ФАЛАЖИ ФОНИДАГИ ПАРАНАЗАЛ СИНУСИТЛАРНИ ДАВОЛАШДА ЎЗИГА ХОС ЁНДАШИШ //MedUnion. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 14-26.

8. Абдурахманов, И. Р., Х. Н. Тураев, and Д. Ф. Шамсиев. "Болаликдан бош мия фалажи фониди риносинусити бор беморларда бурун бўшлиғи мукоцилиар транспорти назорати тўғрисидаги замонавий қарашлар (адабиётлар шарҳи)." журнал «Биомедицины и практики 7.2 (2022): 259-267.
9. Абдурахманов, И., Шамсиев, Д., & Олимжонова, Ф. (2022). ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ МУКОРЕГУЛЯРНЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ОСТРОГО И ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ПАРАНАЗАЛЬНОГО СИНУСИТА ПРИ ДЕТСКОМ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНОМ ПАРАЛИЧЕ. Журнал стоматологии и краниофациальных исследований, 2(2), 18–21. <https://doi.org/10.26739.2181-0966-2021-2-3>
10. Абдурахмонов, Илхом Рустамович. "Тураев Хикматулло Негматович опыт применения синупрета с антибактериальными препаратами в комплексной терапии риносинуситов у больных детским церебральным параличом." Достижения науки и образования 2 (2022): 82.
11. Тураев Хикматилла Негматович, Абдурахмонов Илхом Рустамович ВЛИЯНИЕ БУДЕСониДА НА КАЧЕСТВО ЖИЗНИ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С БРОНХИАЛЬНЫМ ОБСТРУКТИВНЫМ СИНДРОМОМ // Вопросы науки и образования. 2021. №7 (132). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/vliyanie-budesonida-na-kachestvo-zhizni-patsientov-s-bronhialnym-obstruktivnym-sindromom> (дата обращения: 09.10.2023).
12. Абдурахманов И., Шамсиев Д., Олимжонова Ф.(2021) Болаликдан бош мия фалажи билан болалардаги ўткир ва сурункали параназал синуситларни даволашда мукорегуляр дори воситасини самарадорлигини ўрганиш // Журнал стоматологии и краниофациальных исследований, Том2, No2, стр. 18-21